

AN OVERVIEW OF DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES FOR GENERATING MUSICAL COMPOSITIONS

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Abstract

Music generation is increasingly recognized as an attractive field of study in Deep Learning. This paper will focus on a review of the articles that deal with automatic music generation using deep learning methods. A number of well-known architectures, such as Recurrent Neural Network-Long Short-Term Memory (RNN-LSTM), Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Auto-Encoders (VAEs). One aspect of Deep Learning that is currently the most popular is music. Artificial intelligence installation is a method of generating digital music using algorithms, neural networks and other performances. Some scientists came to the conclusion that the effectiveness of the models they consider is gradually being optimized, and the melody is positively correlated with musical coherence and creativity. Thus, in this article, scientists' articles on deep learning methods for creating musical compositions were considered.

Keywords: Deep learning, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Auto-Encoders (VAEs), Recurrent Neural Network-Long Short-Term Memory (RNN-LSTM), Musical Instrument Digital Interface (MIDI).

Introduction

In the modern world, the potential of high technologies is constantly increasing. One of the indicators of the development of modern technologies is Artificial Intelligence (AI), which allows solving tasks that previously could only be performed by a person as a rational being. Many activities can be performed by a machine, a computer; automated types of control, robotics are used, and even machines are endowed with intelligence.

Recently, AI has been applied in various fields of activity, and even in creative areas. One of the newest trends in the world of music is creating music using deep learning. Despite the fact that the creation of such music cannot replace the world's existing musical masterpieces, music creation algorithms using deep learning approaches have positive results.

Currently, deep learning allows creating realistic images and melodies. This article has reviewed the varieties of neural network architectures for music production using deep learning and the effectiveness of neural network architectures for music production.

Music Theory Concepts

To analyze the concepts of music theory, it is necessary to identify ways of presenting musical content. The combination of input and output of the architecture depends on the representation and its encoding. Using the Deep Learning architecture, it is possible to automatically exploit important features from the data. There are Audio and Symbolic architectures that are expressed in different representation types.

The audio representation of music includes signals (waveform), different variations of spectrograms.

Waveform

One of the audio representations is the waveform, which is the raw audio signal or the audio spectrum processed using the Fourier transform [10, p. 17].

Spectrogram

A spectrogram is one of the visual ways of representing a signal, showing the dependence of time on frequency [16].

Symbolic representation of music includes notes, duration, chords, pitch, pauses (rests), intervals, rhythm.

Note – pitch, duration

Note is a musical sound; it is a symbol in music that shows the pitch of a tone. Pitch shows the height and lowness of a sound. Duration is the length of time of the note.

Rhythm

According to the definition, rhythm in music is the placement of sounds in time, the ordered alternation of contrasting elements [1]. Rhythm is the basis of music, implicitly presents in melodies.

Chord

According to Collins dictionary “A chord is a number of musical notes played or sung at the same time with a pleasing effect” [3]. Mostly a chord is a group of 3 or even more notes.

Rest

Rests are pauses in music; they are very important for the construction of a piece of music.

Music presentation formats

The music representation format is necessary for a computer to process a piece of music. The most common formats are 4 main formats, such as MIDI, WAV, text format - ABC notation, piano-roll. Let's take a quick look at each of these formats.

MIDI

Musical Instrument Digital Interface (MIDI) is a technical standard that describes a protocol, a digital interface for interacting with various musical instruments and software [14]. MIDI is a file for recording music and controlling the notes of each musical instrument.

WAV

Waveform Audio File Format (WAV) is an audio file format that is uncompressed and delivers good quality music files. This audio file format is an exact copy of the original music.

ABC notation

With ABC notation it is possible to encode a melody and process it as text. The basic principles of ABC text format encoding rules are note pitch, note longitude. Each line is a letter, which is metadata, followed by the text of the melody itself.

Piano-roll

The Piano-roll format was created to store music in the form of a score matrix. It consists of two axes: vertical and horizontal, which show note pitch and time, note velocities are shown in values.

Varieties of Neural Network Architectures for Music Generation Using Deep Learning

There are many varieties of neural network architectures for music production, this article will consider

the three most common in the generation of music, such as Recurrent Neural Network-Long Short-Term Memory (RNN-LSTM), Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Variational Auto- Encoders (VAEs).

RNN-LSTM

Currently, Recurrent Neural Networks are becoming very popular due to the increasing processing power of GPUs, which are of great importance for serial data, since each neuron can store information in its internal memory about the previous input. RNN has a cyclic connection with its elements, that is, this network has a feedback of one or more elements to each other. The output data of the neuron at the previous stage is broadcast to the same neuron at the next stage [13, p. 2].

Adding Long Short-Term Memory, as shown in Figure 1, is similar to adding a block of memory, allowing to store data for a long time and solve problems such as vanishing gradient and exploding gradient [15].

Figure 1 – RNN-LSTM

<https://towardsdatascience.com/recurrent-neural-networks-56e1ad215339>

GAN

Generative Adversarial Networks (Figure 2) are generative models that consist of two neural networks - Generator and Discriminator. The generator contributes to the creation of new samples, with the help of which the model is trained, and the discriminator classifies these samples into real and fake ones.

Figure 2 – RNN-LSTM

https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Generative-Adversarial-Network-GAN_fig1_317061929

VAE

Variational Auto-Encoders (VAE) - The VAE model uses the Encoder-Decoder architecture to create a latent space through input data recovery [2, p. 2].

The task of the encoder is to take input data and transform it in order to make the representation more compressed. The decoder uses the transformed data to transform it back to its original state. One of the special properties of VAE is that the latent space is continuous,

which facilitates random transformations and interpolation. VAE architecture is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – VAE

<https://learnopencv.com/variational-autoencoder-in-tensorflow/>

Results

Around one hundred articles have been studied, and ten of them were chosen as mostly related to current study. We compiled a comparative table in which the authors share their results with different architectures. We have defined the format of "Architecture and Music", "Architecture Characteristics", "Metric Type" and "Metric Value" for the table 1 and review the research paper in these ten selected articles according to these parameters (Table 1 - The effectiveness of various architectures).

Hao-Wen Dong and Yi-Hsuan Yang "Convolutional generative adversarial networks with binary neurons for polyphonic music generation". The authors consider GAN/Piano roll in their article. According to the authors of this article the length of the input random vector is 128. The authors use the Adam optimizer and only apply batch normalization to Generator and Refiner. The authors apply "the slope annealing trick to networks with Binary Neurons, where the slope of the sigmoid function in the sigmoid-adjusted straight-through estimator is multiplied by 1:1 after each epoch". They described that "The batch size is 16 except for the first stage in the two-stage training setting, where the batch size is 32" [6, p. 5].

Jiyanbo Cao, Maolin Qi, Jinan Fiaidhi "A Review of Automatic Music Generation Based on Performance RNN". The authors consider RNN-LSTM/MIDI. According to the authors the basic RNN architecture consists of 3 layers of LSTMs, and 512 cells in each layer. "The input is a 413-dimensional one-hot vector, as is the target, and the model outputs a categorical distribution over the same dimensionality as well." [11, p. 3]. So, the authors believe that for generation, the output is sampled with beam search, and for training, is used teacher forcing.

Ziyu Wang, Yiyi Zhang, et al. "Pianotree VAE: structured representation learning for Polyphonic music". The article is devoted to VAE/ Piano-roll. The piano-roll recurrent VAE is similar to a 2-bar MusicVAE. According to the information, given in the article "the hidden dimensions of the GRU encoder and decoder are both 1024" [18, p. 4]. Piano VAE convolutional architecture uses a convolutional-deconvolutional architecture. The kernel size is 33 in the convolutional layers, of which there are eight in total. The authors described

this architecture in a following way "Strided convolution is performed at the 3rd, 5th, 7th and 8th layer with stride size (2x1); (2x3); (2x2) and (2x2) respectively. The decoder adopts the deconvolution operations in a reversed order" [18, p. 4]. The piano-roll fully-connected VAE (pr-fc) architecture applies 256-dimensional embedding layer which is time-distributed, then 3 fully-connected layers with the hidden dimensions follow with the hidden dimensions [1024, 768] for the encoder. And decoder accepts counter operations in a reversed order. Then authors characterize "The MIDI-like event recurrent VAE (midi-seq) adopts the recurrent model structure similar to pr-rnn. Here, the event vocabulary contains 128 "note-on", 128 "noteoff" and 32 "time shift" tokens. The embedding size of a single MIDI event is 128. The hidden dimensions of the encoder GRU and decoder GRU are 512 and 1024 respectively [18, p. 4].

Jay A. Hennig, Akash Umakantha Ryan C. Williamson "A Classifying Variational Autoencoder with Application to Polyphonic Music Generation". The article is about VAE and VAE+LSTM/Piano-roll. For the VAE+LSTM standard, the authors implement a network similar to STORN. In this case, each encoder and decoder network is replaced by an LSTM followed by a dense layer, i.e. the equations given in the article also depend on the latent conditions of the LSTM. The classification of VAE+LSTM is similar except of classifier addition realized in analogy with VAE classification. Take into account that the classifier is given the whole sequence X of length T to classify the key. For the classification of VAE, $T = 1$, and for the classification of VAE + LSTM the authors consider the sequence length as a hyperparameter [9].

Gautam Mittal, Jesse Engel, et al. "Symbolic music generation with diffusion models". The authors used VAE/ MIDI. The authors believe that their model learns to generate discrete sequences of notes by first training the VAE with sequence parameters and then training the distribution model to capture the timing relationships among k latent VAEs. Sequence VAEs such as MusicVAE, is difficult for training on long sequences and the authors try to overcome it combining the short 2-bar MusicVAE model with a diffusion model which is able to model dependencies between $k = 32$ latents, thus modeling 64 bars in total [4].

Xinru Li and Yizhen Niu “Research on Chord-Constrained Two-Track Music Generation Based on Improved GAN Networks”. The authors used GAN/nope format, then converted to MIDI. According to the authors “A typical three-layer neural network framework, including an input layer, a hidden layer, an activation layer, an output layer, and a normalization process for the output. The neural network graph has three neurons in the input layer and four neurons in the hidden layer. An activation function is added after the hidden layer to add a nonlinear factor to the results of the matrix operations, mapping the features to a high-dimensional nonlinear interval for interpretation. The output layer has two neurons, and the output of the output layer is normalized so that the data are restricted to a certain range, thus eliminating the undesirable effects caused by odd sample data” [17, p. 2].

Hao-Wen Dong, Wen-Yi Hsiao, et al. “MuseGAN: Multi-track Sequential Generative Adversarial Networks for Symbolic Music Generation and Accompaniment”. The article is about GAN/ Piano roll. The authors of the article based on the analyses of Gulrajani et al. 2017, according to whom “Both G and D are implemented as deep CNNs. G grows the time axis first and then the pitch axis, while D compresses in the opposite way” [7, p. 5]. They update G once every five updates to D and apply batch normalization only to G. The total length of the input random vector for each generator is fixed at 128.9. Training time for each model is less than 24 hours with Tesla K40m. In the testing phase, the authors binarize the output G, which uses the tangent as the activation function in the last phase with a threshold at zero.

Hao-Min Liu, Yi-Hsuan Yang “Lead Sheet Generation and Arrangement by Conditional Generative Adversarial Network”. The authors considered GAN/MIDI. The Gtemp in the lead sheet of the model of generation is realized by “two-layer RNN with 4 outputs and 32 hidden units. Gbar, G(c) bar, D and D(c) are all implemented as CNNs. The total size of the input random vectors z for Gbar and G(c) bar are both set to 128. For the encoder E in arrangement generation” [5, p. 4].

The authors used missed connections and used other topology for coding three features. They use WGAN-gp for model training. Each model is trained with a Tesla K80m GPU less than in 24 hours and the size of batch is 64.

Ke Chen, Cheng-i Wang, et al “Music SketchNet: controllable music generation via Factorized representations of pitch and rhythm”. The authors used VAE/MIDI. According to the authors of the article

Music SketchNet consists of three components:

(1) SketchVAE is a new variational autoencoder which converts music dimensions into high dimensional latent variables. Using factorized inference network, SketchVAE divides latent variables into two parts: the pitch contour and rhythm which serve as the control parameters for users.

(2) SketchInpainter contains stacked recurrent networks to handle the element-level inpainting prediction in the latent space [12, p. 2].

(3) SketchConnector receives users’ sketches of pitch, rhythm, or both, combines them with the prediction from SketchInpainter, and finalizes the generation [12, p. 2].

Hsiao-Tzu Hung, Chung-Yang Wang, et al “Improving Automatic Jazz Melody Generation by Transfer Learning Techniques”. The authors used VAE/MIDI. The authors consider recurrent VAE model. In the encoder part, four-bar melody sequences are sent to the bidirectional gated recurrent units (BGRU) to study the correlation between bars. Then the outputs of all GRU time steps unite and move through several tense, means fully-connected) layers for getting the embedding vector. Taking into consideration the observing input melody x, the encoder E with parameter set encodes x into a latent vector $z = E(x)$. According to the authors in the decoder part, a latent vector z is sampled from a normal distribution characterized and then passes through several fully-connected layers, parameterized for separate formation of initial states of the melody. “The outputs are processed by a unidirectional GRU with a sigmoid activation layer to finally output a four-bar pianoroll” [8, p. 3].

Table 1

The effectiveness of various architectures

№	Architecture/ Music format	Architecture Characteristics	Metric type	Metric value
1	GAN/ Piano roll	The Adam optimizer; batch normalization to Generator and Refiner	1. Qualified note rate(QN) 2. Polyphonicity (PP) 3. Tonal distance (TD)	According to the metrics selected by the authors, QN calculates the ratio of the number of qualified notes to the total number of notes. With a low QN, the music is overly fragmented. PP shows the ratio of the number of time steps when playing two notes to the total number of time steps. TD measures the distance between the color features of a pair of tracks in tonal space. TDs between piano and guitar are the two most used tracks [6].
2	RNN- LSTM/ MIDI	The basic RNN architecture consists of 3 layers of LSTMs, and 512 cells in each layer	In the evaluation matrix, the logarithm of losses is used because, according to the authors, the musical expression is not the meaning of the signal that can state the result.	Log Loss is the most important feature-based classification metric. It is difficult to interpret pending log loss values, but log loss is an appropriate metric for comparing models. A lower log loss is better for any given problem [11].
3	VAE/ Piano- roll	Piano VAE convolutional architecture uses a convolutional-deconvolutional architecture. The kernel size is 33 in the convolutional layers, of which there are eight in total.	Objective evaluation: -Onset precision - Onset recall - Onset F1 -Duration Precision -Duration Recall -Duration F1 Subjective evaluation: -overall musicality - smoothness of transition	Objective evaluation An objective assessment is presented in the form of a comparison of various models in terms of their exact restoration of the beginning of the fundamental tone and the duration of notes, which are most often used in musical information retrieval tasks. For the accuracy of the duration of the note, according to the authors, only those notes are taken into account, the beginning and height of which are built correctly. Subjective evaluation To do this, the authors invite people to subjectively evaluate the models through a double-blind online survey. During the survey, listeners first listen to a couple of musical compositions, and then listen to 5 interpolation options [18].
4	VAE and VAE+ LSTM/ Piano- roll	The authors implement a network similar to STORN	Average number of notes; Tone span.	Average number of notes - average number of notes played at each time step; Tone span - The average distance between the highest and lowest pitch in each sample. The authors present these quantitative measures as “a first approximation of the samples’ musical quality”, however they mark a more thorough evaluation of the music will require the subjective evaluation of experienced musicians [9].

5	VAE/ MIDI	The model learns to generate discrete sequences of notes by first training the VAE with sequence parameters and then training the distribution model to capture the timing relationships among k latent VAEs.	Modified framewise Overlapping Area (OA) metric; Fréchet distance (FD); Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD).	<p>In order to assess the statistical similarity between qualitative results of the model and the original training sequences, the authors provide the metric, which fixes the local models of self-similarity in generated melodic sequences. The authors evaluate their models with a modified framewise Overlapping Area (OA) metric.</p> <p>The authors use a sliding 4-bar window with a 2-bar jump size to capture local statistics on the pitch and duration of the piece. They then calculate the average pitch value, which determines the melodic similarity, as well as the duration, which reflects the rhythmic similarity in each 4-bar frame. These statistics determine the Gaussian PDF for pitch and duration for each frame (pP(k); pD(k)).</p> <p>The authors evaluate the similarity of “latent embedding generated by each of the models using the Fréchet distance (FD) and Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) with a polynomial kernel”.</p> <p>It is important to note that this metric does not measure the long-term timing or quality of generated sequences, but only the quality of the intermediate continuous representation before the final sequence is generated by the MusicVAE decoder [4].</p>
6	GAN/ nope format, then	The neural network graph has three neurons in the	The core method of assessment is based on	A total of 50 people were evaluated, including 40 general listeners and 10 music professionals (musicians or instrumentalists), and three groups of
	converted to MIDI	input layer and four neurons in the hidden layer. An activation function is added after the hidden layer to add a nonlinear factor to the results of the matrix operations, mapping the features to a high-dimensional nonlinear interval for interpretation.	subjective assessment of the user. Survey among users. There are three indicators of the effectiveness of assessment: coherence, earliness, and innovation.	<p>results were evaluated for their melodic connection, fearfulness and creativity.</p> <p>The results were evaluated on a five-point scale, where 1 is the least effective indicator, 5 is the most effective, etc. The weighted average is 50 points [17].</p>
7	GAN/ Piano roll	Both G and D are implemented as deep CNNs. G grows the time axis first and then the pitch axis, while D compresses in the opposite way.	EB – empty bars; UPC – used pitch classes; QN - qualified notes; DP - drum pattern; TD - tonal distance.	<p>EB - ratio of empty bars (in %).</p> <p>UPC - number of used pitch classes per bar (from 0 to 12).</p> <p>QN - ratio of “qualified” notes (in %). The authors study a note not shorter than three beats (i.e. a 32th note) as a qualified note. QN shows if the music is extremely fragmented.</p> <p>DP - drum pattern: ratio of notes in 8- or 16-beat patterns, common ones for Rock songs in 4/4 time (in %).</p> <p>TD - tonal distance. It measures the harmony between a couple of tracks [7].</p>

8	GAN/ MIDI	The authors used missed connections and used other topology for coding three features.	Objective metrics are the same as in MuseGAN: EB – empty bars; UPC – used pitch classes; QN - qualified notes; DP - drum pattern; TD - tonal distance. User Study – mean opinion score (MOS).	User study. The meaning of it is the users are asked to vote for the best model among the three taking into consideration the harmonicas, rhythmicity and overall feeling, respectively [5].
9	VAE/ MIDI	Music SketchNet consists of three components: SketchVAE SketchInpainter SketchConnector	The authors chose three criteria: the number of notes (difficulty), the repetition of musical structures (structure), and the degree of harmony of the music.	Before the songs are evaluated, the recipients will see a description of the three criteria that the authors of the article presented. The rating ranges from 1.0 to 5.0 in increments of 0.5. The authors collected 318 survey results from 106 recipients (each recipient listens to three groups, 9 melodies in total) [12].
10	VAE/ MIDI	The authors consider recurrent VAE model.	The functions related to the pitch describe the preferences for arranging pitch: Pitch count (PC); Pitch class histogram (PCH); Pitch class transition matrix (PCTM); Pitch range (PR); The functions related to the rhythm describe the note arrangement: Note count (NC); Note length histogram (NLH); Note length transition matrix (NLTM).	“Pitch count (PC) - The pitch count is the number of unique pitches within a phrase. The output is a scalar for each phrase. Pitch class histogram (PCH) - The pitch class histogram is a 12-dimensional, octave-independent representation of the pitch content for achromatic scale” [8, p. 4]. Pitch class transition matrix (PCTM): The transition of the pitch contains useful information for definition of tonality, chord recognition, and genre recognition. “The two-dimensional pitch class transition matrix is a histogram-like representation by counting the pitch transitions for each (ordered) pair of notes. The resulting matrix size is 1212” [8, p. 4]. Pitch range (PR): The pitch range is calculated as the difference between the highest and lowest MIDI pitches in semitones within a phrase. The output is a scalar for each phrase. Note count (NC): The note count is the number of notes in the phrase. In the opposite to the pitch count the note count contains not the information on pitch but the function related to rhythm which records only the number of notes in the phrase. The output is a scalar for each phrase. Note length histogram (NLH): In order to extract the note length histogram, the authors define a set of allowable beat length classes. The length of a bar is defined as to contain
				96 unites of length and each length of the note is quantized to the nearest number of unit lengths. The option “rest” if it is activated doubles the size of the vector in order to present the same length classes for rests. “The output vector has a length of either 12 (for notes) or 24 (12 for notes and 12 for rests), respectively” [8, p. 4]. “Note length transition matrix (NLTM): Similar to PCTM, the note length transition matrix provides useful information for rhythm description. The matrix size is 1212 or 2424” [8, p. 4].

Conclusion

In this article, we have analyzed various articles regarding automatic music creation using deep learning techniques. In different articles, the authors use different metrics and different architectures and music formats. For a long time, researchers have tried to solve the problem of algorithmic music generation using computational models and various architectures. Having studied a large number of scientific articles on automatic music generation using deep learning methods, we can conclude that all these architectures mentioned in this article are effective and relevant.

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